

Determinations of Mercaptopyrimidines and Preparation of Their Silver Derivatives

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A volumetric method has been developed for the determination of 2-mercaptopyrimidines (Ia-Ie). The determination has been extended to analysis of a mercaptopyrimidine and a thiocyanate when present together in a mixture; and is based on the chemical reactions where silver nitrate reacts quantitatively with the thiocyanate and the mercaptopyrimidine in the molar ratios of 1 and 2 respectively, in the presence of ammonia. The other 2-mercaptopyrimidines (If-II) under the same conditions form their silver derivatives (IIa-IIg). The silver derivatives have also been analysed.

OXIDIMETRIC methods¹ for the determination of thioureas are well known and the same have been applied to the estimations of 2-mercaptopyrimidines². Thiourea has also been determined by the use of silver nitrate reagent^{3,4}. In an attempt to apply the latter procedure⁴ to the determination of 2-mercaptopyrimidines, we have found that some of the 2-mercaptopyrimidines (Ia-Ie) can be determined successfully, while others (If-II) form their silver derivatives.

A 2-mercaptopyrimidine (Ia-Ie) reacts quantitatively with 2 moles equivalents of silver nitrate in the presence of ammonia to give silver sulphide; the grey precipitate starts appearing immediately.

In the case of other 2-mercaptopyrimidines (If-II) no grey precipitate appears, on the other hand white to bright yellow silver derivatives (IIa-IIg) precipitate out. The compound Im when reacted with silver nitrate under the described conditions immediately forms a white coloured precipitate which

starts changing to black. The complete change to silver sulphide does not take place even when boiled for 30 mins. making its analysis difficult.

Experimental

All mercaptopyrimidines were prepared by the method of Mathes⁵ and purified by repeated crystallisations from suitable solvents.

0.1*N* solution of silver nitrate was prepared by dissolving 16.989 g. of the desiccated silver nitrate AR (BDH) in water and making the volume to one litre.

Decinormal ammonium thiocyanate solution was prepared by dissolving 8.0 g. of the dried AR (BDH) compound in water and making the volume to one litre, followed by standardisation against 0.1*N* silver nitrate, using ferric alum as the indicator.

The indicator was prepared by dissolving 1.0 g. of the ferric alum (BDH) in water. 1-2 ml of nitric acid was added to make the solution clear followed by dilution to 100 ml with water.

Ammonia solution and nitric acid were BDH reagents diluted to desired strengths with water.

Determination of 2-mercaptopyrimidines: A known wt. (10-100 mg.) of a 2-mercaptopyrimidine (Ia-Ie) was taken in a titration flask and dissolved in hot ethanol (10-25 ml). While the solution was hot a known excess of 0.1*N* silver nitrate (10-25 ml.) was added followed by approximately 2*N* ammonium hydroxide in order to adjust the strength with res-

pect to ammonia within 0.25–2*N*. The flask was loosely stoppered and the contents were gently boiled for 4–5 min (7–8 min in case of Ic and Id) and cooled to room temperature. The mixture was then acidified with approximately 8*N* nitric acid so that the acidity ranged between 1–2*N* with respect to nitric acid. The precipitated silver sulphide was filtered and washed with water. The unreacted silver nitrate in the filtrate and washings was titrated against 0.1*N* ammonium thiocyanate solution, using 4–5 drops of the ferric alum indicator to the appearance of pink colour.

If *V* denotes the volume (in ml.) of *N* normal silver nitrate solution consumed by *W* mg. of the 2-mercaptopyrimidine (mol. wt. *M*), then

$$W = \frac{1}{2} VNM$$

Some typical results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF 2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINES (Ia–Ie)

Compound	Taken mg.	Found mg.	Deviation %
Ia (R = methyl group)	10.6	10.6	0.000
	86.0	85.8	-0.232
Ib (R = ethyl group)	19.5	19.6	0.513
	71.2	71.6	0.562
Ic (R = <i>n</i> -butyl group)	14.7	14.8	0.680
	93.1	93.4	0.322
Id (R = iso-butyl group)	11.2	11.2	0.000
	99.5	99.8	0.302
Ie (R = allyl group)	10.4	10.4	0.000
	88.2	88.6	0.451

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYSES OF SILVER DERIVATIVES (IIa–IIg)

Compound	Colour	Yield %	m.p.* °C	Taken mg.	Found mg.
IIa (R = hydrogen)	White	95	224	28.2	28.08
IIb (R = sec-butyl group)	Bright yellow	80	220	36.5	36.04
IIc (R = benzyl group)	White	95	254	35.0	34.80
IId (R = phenyl group)	Dirty white	85	246	29.7	29.52
IIe (R = <i>p</i> -tolyl group)	Dirty white	90	249	34.2	34.06
IIf (R = <i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl)	White	95	248	33.5	33.24
IIg (R = <i>m</i> -nitrophenyl)	Pale yellow	85	250	39.5	39.36

* All compounds melted with decomposition. The m.p. are uncorrected. The compounds could not be recrystallised from any solvent.

The results show that the 2-mercaptopyrimidines (Ia–Ie) can be determined in the range of 10–100 mg. with an accuracy of $\pm 0.7\%$.

The method becomes of particular interest when a mercaptopyrimidine is present in a mixture with a thiocyanate (sodium, potassium or ammonium thiocyanate). In such circumstances, oxidative procedures^{1,2} fail but by the use of this method both the

mercaptopyrimidine and the thiocyanate can be simultaneously determined. Silver nitrate reacts with thiocyanates and 2-mercaptopyrimidines in the molar ratios of 1 and 2. The individual amounts of thiocyanate and 2-mercaptopyrimidine in the mixture can be calculated⁶.

Preparation of the silver derivatives: A known wt. (100–200 mg.) of the 2-mercaptopyrimidine (If–II) was dissolved in minimum quantity of hot alcohol. To this solution, 1.1 mole equivalent of silver nitrate dissolved in water added while hot followed by a few ml (2–5) of ammonia solution. The alcohol was evaporated over boiling water bath until the precipitated derivative coagulated. It was then separated by filtration, thoroughly washed with water and dried in oven at 110° for 1 hr.

The silver salts are slightly soluble in ether and form colloidal solutions in ethanol. The colours, yields and m.p. of various derivatives are recorded in Table 2.

Analysis of silver derivatives: Ammonium ceric sulphate method² was slightly modified.

A known wt. (25–50 mg.) of the silver salt (IIa–IIg) was suspended in 10 ml of ethanol, followed by 10 ml of 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid to make a homogeneous solution. A drop of ferroin indicator was added and the solution titrated against 0.05*N* ammonium ceric sulphate, to the change of colour from red to blue. Typical analyses are recorded in table 2.

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